

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

STRATEGIES OF SPEECH MASKS IN RADIO DISCOURSE

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Abstract

A fragment of a comprehensive study on the identification of role-masks as components of the game in the media text is presented. The purpose of the work is to create a typology of role-masks presented in the communicative space of radio. Strategies of entertaining, status and communicative-regulatory mask roles, their dominant lexical markers are described. The functions of the identified roles-masks are established: providing convenience for the perception of scientific information, consolidating, therapeutic, hedonistic, the function of putting forward a significant idea, etc.

Keywords: radio, discourse, speech masks, communicative strategy, tactics.

In the communicative space of radio a special game continuum is organized with the help of speech masks system. The mosaic nature of the images of the author and the addressee is reflected in the "split" of the author's images, which is represented in the communicative space through strategies. Gaming and communicative-regulatory strategies are associated with the creation of a speech mask in entertainment media texts as a special speech-behavioral model. They are important elements of the structure of the media text and allow solving various communicative tasks. The essence of these strategies is to transform the addresser into another linguistic personality. They are based on linguistic "joking", humor with a mindset for fun, the creation of hedonistic emotions among the addressees, as well as outrageous, theatrical and entertaining.

The radio discourse reflects the subject-subject focus on the formation of entertaining-playing, phatic interaction between the presenter and the listener. It is coordinated on the basis of the speech behavior (presentation) of the presenter and the organization of emotional and axiological community with the addressee due to the communicative strategies of the speech mask. The aim of the article is to identify the dominant communicative strategies and tactics of speech masks in entertainment and informative radio discourse. The research material consists of 400 radio programs broadcast by Belarusian radio channels from 2000 to 2023.

The communicative-pragmatic functions of the radio discourse provide the following strategies: *entertaining*, *status* and *communicative-regulatory speech masks*.

Strategies of Speech Masks in Entertainment Radio Discourse

Orientation towards the hedonistic orientation of interaction, communicative hedonism (pleasure from communication), which are the pragmatic dominants of the radio discourse, is actively manifested through the tactical repertoire of *entertainment strategies speech masks (SM) Cheerful and Joker*.

The entertaining and playful beginning can be traced in the implementation of the tactics of SM *Cheerful*: *humor* (1), *funny story* (2), *self-criticism* (3), *dispute* (4), which create a system of communicative attractions that make up a structural and meaningful text whole: Moderator: *Your task is to determine, where is the fake with us ...* (3) *Just turn off the receiver, otherwise I hear myself. And my voice infuriates me, especially in the morning.* Presenter: *And your wife lives with you and hears this every day!* Moderator: (1) *I represent, of course, and I get paid every day for it. So, first news. ...* Presenter: *The second news. The news at the Oslo Institute, this is Norway, there is such a city ... They created a special electric sheet. ...* Host: *I mean, are you normal? Do you have electric sheet?* (1) *Yes, I went off the air! I'm surrounded by people with electric sheets! Where is my straitjacket? My cat warms me!* ("Fake or not fake", Radio Unistar, 09.09.20).

The actualization of the entertaining mode is promoted by colloquial, pejorative vocabulary - manifestations of the tactics of self-criticism; emotional-evaluative regulatives, language game - markers of humor tactics; vocabulary-markers of disagreement (oh, come on, it's not true, etc.). Such attractive demonstrators are intended for the pleasure of the audience, often consisting of "a carnival reversal of stereotyped ideas, opinions and behaviors" [Karasik, p. 232].

The communicative style of SM *Cheerful*, which is typical for an entertaining conversational radio, is characterized by a high proportion of humor, parody, theatricality, spontaneity and play. Among the most recurrent objects that *Cheerful* humor is directed at are situations and facts from the personal life of the host and participants in communicative interaction, the participants in the program and their abilities, qualities and skills of the host, as well as interpersonal relationships.

Strategy of SM *Joker* is implemented by clowning tactics, the most common in radio broadcasts in the period 2000-2018. The clownish nature of the communicative interaction is supported by the host's parodying someone else's behavior (a woman, a young girl, etc.) in a conversation with the listener, distortion, mangling

of sounds, changing the stress in words to create a laughable effect.

The strategies of *communicative-regulatory speech masks* act as a means of embodying an emotionally-adjusting discourse plan that intimizes communicative interaction and forms an emotional atmosphere, the mood of the audience. The emotional, axiological space of sincerity, built on the basic needs of recognition, respect and internal interests of the audience, can be considered as a discursive ideology of radio. Ideology in this case is understood in its broadest sense - as a system of value meanings implicitly present in the genre and language ways of organizing content, a system that manifests itself in the process of "unconscious" displacement "of obligatory units (rethinking, modal interpretation) towards" discursive interests " [Rezanova, p. 60]. Its formation is aimed at modeling a sense of community (experience, life stories, emotions, etc.), spiritual, cordial relationships with the addressee. Social relationships of all kinds are the more real, reliable and authentic, the closer they affect the internal psychological interests of everyone [Batsenkova, p. 135].

To create a friendly area where the listener can feel meaningful and valued the radio discourse employs the strategy of *SM Inspiring Well-Wisher*.

Emotionally shaping dominants in radio serve to involve the addressee in communicative interaction, to attract attention - tactics that implement the strategy of Inspiring well-wisher: *indications of acceptance, praise, demonstration of the significance of the addressee, wishes*.

The communicative space of radio in recent years is being formed as a space for a special way of thinking - *acceptance*, which researchers define as "a worldview position expressed in an unconditional value attitude to life, to oneself and others, which is developed in the process of developing life experience on the basis of a conscious choice of respect for diversity of the surrounding world ... recognition of the diversity, multivariance, otherness of everything that exists and agreement with this" [Ryazantseva]. The ideals of the "new sincerity" - honesty, openness and authenticity - determine the implementation of this category in the communicative tactics of indicating acceptance, the markers of which are statements of a stating nature containing inclusive pronouns and lexemes with the meaning of difference, uniqueness: *You see how different we are all* (Radio Rocks); *Everyone feels and lives in their own way, we are all different, unique* (Radio New Wave); *Yes, there are strange situations like this* (Radio Minsk).

The tactics of praise reflects the axiological dominant of modern radio - sensitivity, "new sincerity", expressed in increased sensitivity. Emotional regulatives become linguistic manifestations (*clever! Ah, well done!*), emotional-evaluative vocabulary demonstrating a high degree of quality, vocabulary of uniqueness semantics, designations of emotions (*proud, respect, rejoice*): *But such a unique thing as yours, Tatyana, is not no one will have. There will be no such risk somewhere in a cafe to meet a girl in the same dress. I'm sure it's a cool experience and incredible skills! ... Tell your*

stories ... be sure to share what it is, your way. I'm sure there is something to be proud of! (Radio Unistar, 03.03.2023).

The *tactic of demonstrating the significance of the addressee* is aimed at emphasizing the desirability of contact with a partner, recognizing the importance of his communicative interests and communicative efforts due to the lexemes of the semantics of importance, necessity; friendly treatment (friends, our loved ones): *Friends, your opinion and your stories are important to us* (Minsk Wave); *We call you now to our studio, our dear news experts. This is because we can't do without you* ("News Expert", Radio Rocks, 09/27/2022).

The *tactic of wishing* is a discursive marker of the communicative space of radio, as it creates the basis for headlines, phatic speech genres (greeting, farewell), as well as dialogic interaction between the presenter and the addressee, for example, *Live greedily, take everything from life!* ("Finally a show", Radio Unistar, 2018); *Have a productive day for everyone and have a good mood!* (Radio Rocks VKontakte, 2022).

An emotionally rich communicative space focused on reducing the distance between information and the addressee is formed by the tactics of gratitude, which often constitutes a communicative model in combination with other tools of communicative-regulatory speech masks strategies (tactics of praise, demonstrating the significance of the addressee, etc.): *Come on, we are waiting for your wonderful, frank stories. ... Our dear listeners, thank you all for trusting us and sincerely sharing your interesting stories. ... Let everything in your life be super, super, super!* (Radio Rocks, 2022).

Strategies of Speech Masks in Informative Radio Discourse

The picture of communicative interaction with the addressee in informative radio discourse is formed by the entertainment strategies of SM Cheerful and Refuter as well as status strategy of speech masks *One of your, Expert*.

Monologic radio genres, characteristic of the 20th - early 21st centuries, were transformed into dialogic ones. This entailed a transformation of the role of the journalist. The desire of a journalist to thin out the information density and form a hedonistic space for obtaining knowledge gives rise to the use of entertaining strategies of speech masks. The strategy of SM Cheerful is the most typical for dialogic cognitive genres. It is represented by tactics of *humorous commentary, humorous mockery, and humor*.

In the radio discourse, polyphony is represented mainly by thematic and tonal-stylistic (changing the tone and style of communication) variability, which manifests itself in the generation of a secondary thematic line when discussing a cognitive topic. The polyphony of switching is ensured by editing cognitive topics (presented by an expert) and topics that provide a phatic resource, an emotional background for communication, which are updated through idle speech communication of the hosts on the air: Host: *Is strip plastic not suitable for men? Well, you never know. Expert: Everything is possible in the modern world. Pre-*

sender 2: *If you decide to change your career so drastically, then we will support you, of course.* Presenter 1: *This is all that I can do with my own hands.* Presenter: *It's probably more about legs, plastic strip.* Presenter 2: *You don't see, the person is starting.* Presenter 1: *You haven't seen my numbers, Katya, just wait* ("Guest on the topic", Radio Mir, 02/07/2023).

The axiological dominant of the radio discourse - conflict - gets deliberately marked in the strategy of SM Refuter. The clash of opinions of the expert and the presenter or several presenters of the program contributes to the activation of the attractive (emotional, entertaining) side of communication. Tactically, the Refuter's is actualized through the tactics of dispute as a *provocation (source of information), dispute as an exchange of opinions.*

In the course of communicative interaction, the text-forming model of a cognitive text is implemented by the strategies of the status of speech masks of a journalist. The structure of instructive genres is made up of the following tactical model of the speech mask *Expert: tactics of advice, instruction, commentary, approval/disapproval*, which demonstrates ordinary knowledge or assessment, contrasting with the knowledge or analysis of the expert: Presenter: *In such a situation, that they themselves got, respectively, exactly you can get out of there. In no case do not refuse to colleagues, in no case do not refuse close acquaintances to help neighbors. But do it a little bit, little by little, cutting back on the amount of help that you provide. ...* Psychologist: *On the one hand, I agree. On the other hand, I have some internal contradictions. I'll explain now. Look here, imagine the situation. Everyone is used to the fact that Olga does all the work for them, and no matter how much she puts a little bit of boundaries back, people still won't understand this. ...* Olya, *you set the time frame* ("Formula of Happiness", Radio Unistar, 10/22/2018). The contrast of everyday and expert knowledge becomes the structural and content engine of the radio text.

The role of the translator of knowledge has changed to the role represented by the speech mask *One of you* as a representative who voices the impressions

and interests of the media audience. The host broadcasts on the air potential objections, the emotions of the listener. This strategy, which manifests itself in the tactics of *bewilderment, objection, agreement, disagreement, evaluation*, is aimed at reflecting the intended or potential opinion and feelings of the listener in order to include him as much as possible in the communicative situation, as well as demonstrate closeness (communicative and psychological), form equal relations: Expert: *At this time of the year, some citizens try to feed (ducks) and in this way we disrupt the natural process of bird migration. That is, the birds do not fly away.* Host: *So what? I would like to ask the harsh scientists. Are you walking with a child in the park and no contact with the cute world of birds? Are you just looking at them? And all? Or maybe sometimes you can still feed the birds?* ("Green world. We feed the birds in the park", Radio Mir, 2022).

To conclude, it's necessary to point out that speech mask strategies act as a structure-forming element of the communicative space of a media text. They actively form a trusting, friendly, informative or inspiring, playful, jokingly ironic or mocking tone of an entertaining media text. Being aimed at the organization of communication, speech mask strategies provide convenience in the perception of information, perform entertaining, hedonistic and therapeutic functions.

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